

THE ROLE OF COMMUNICATION IN HUMAN LIFE.

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Summary

The article analyzes the multifaceted process of cooperation between people the development of communication with them and the role of communication in the formation the spiritual imade of a person. Communication is unique to all living beings creatures and is most developed precisely human level. It was said the satisfaction of almost all the nedds of a person of a different kind is propess that saps on how well catered it is communication nedds. The analizing in communication of person has a lot of thinking goals and process of knowing the world.

Key words: communication, language, needs, thinking, consciousness, speech, perception, information, personality, communication.

Communication is a human need as a social, conscious being, as a carrier of consciousness. Communication is defined as the interaction between two or more people in the exchange of information that has the nature of knowledge or affective evaluation. As a biosocial, spiritual and spiritual being, man has various needs. It is in the process of meeting these needs that a person is formed, develops, and develops his spiritual image. It would not be wrong to say that the need for communication is the most important in the system of human needs. After all, the satisfaction of almost all other needs of a person is related to the satisfaction of his need for communication. In the process of communicating with people around him, he informs them about all his needs and enters into social relations with those around him. Communication is common to all living things. It is at the level of people that it has the most refined forms, it is realized through speech. Speech is a powerful factor in the formation of a person's mental maturity.

Communication is a form of living, and in this process, a person creates new knowledge and skills, experience, and in turn delivers this knowledge and experience to others as a result of new communication.

According to the Russian philosopher R.S. Nemov, "Communication occurs in almost all living beings. But at the human level, communication reaches its highest level, it acquires aspects such as consciousness, aesthetics and goal orientation, and most importantly, it reaches its highest level through the

medium of speech. Just as important vital elements in the human body move through the human body and ensure its vitality, communication is the main factor that ensures such vitality in the system of social relations of society. Communication is a process of sharing communication, influencing each other, understanding others, establishing and developing communication between people, arising from the needs of joint action.

There are both verbal and non-verbal means of communication. Language is a means of communication. Language ensures communication between the participants, because it is understood by both the informer and the receiver. The person giving information to another person (communicator) and receiving it (receiver) must use the same language during communication, otherwise they cannot understand each other properly. The exchange of information should have signs and content that are understandable to the participants. Language consists of a set of word symbols. The meaning of the word is its substantive aspect. Actions and activities of each individual are determined by 3 important factors. First, it is determined by the socio-historical experience of the entire humanity or a narrow group of people.

A small child does not know the world independently, he asks his parents questions and they answer him, from these answers the child receives only a small part of the general knowledge that he uses later in his career. A child can form this small part of general knowledge in the form of language, using language in the system of word symbols. It is the same at school, the student acquires all his knowledge and skills about the world from the teacher's explanation or from the textbook, that is, with the help of language. Here, language fulfills one of its important tasks, i.e. means of living, as a means of imparting and mastering socio-historical experience.

Secondly, the actions and activities of each individual are often determined by the direct experiences of other people who do not have social value.

A person's "personal" experience, his own individual experience, consists of a unique mixture of other people's experiences and social experience. A person, unlike an animal, can plan his actions. Language is the main tool for such planning and solving common intellectual problems. Here we came across the third function of language as a tool of mental activity (perception, memory, thinking, imagination). As a system of word signs, language is used in speech activity.

To date, mankind has not invented a more effective mechanism for organizing, managing and regulating social relations between people than communication.

According to researchers, human civilization would not have existed if the most ancient ancestors of mankind had not thought of communicating. Because, in the process of communication, a person exchanges information and information with others, spreads what he knows to others, and learns what he does not know from others.

Communication is a multifaceted process of development of communication between people based on the needs of their cooperative activities. Communication includes the exchange of information between the participants of cooperative activities, which represents the communicative aspect of communication. People use language as a means of communication when communicating with each other. The second side of the communication is the interaction of the participants. In this, not only words are exchanged, but also actions and situations. For example, a transaction between a seller and a buyer can be made without saying a word.

The third aspect of communication is the perception of the participants. It is important for the participants to understand each other correctly. Thus, three conditional aspects of communication can be distinguished: communicative (giving information), interactive (interaction) and perceptive (mutual perception). The unity of these three aspects of communication is manifested as a method of externalization of interaction and cooperative activity of people entering into communication.

It is very important for a pedagogue to know the laws of communication, the formation of skills and abilities. This ensures full-fledged pedagogical communication or interaction. Pedagogical communication is a set of methods of interaction between the teacher and students.

The content of the communication is the exchange of information, mutual understanding and externalization of mutual relations with the students by the teacher using various communication tools. Educational and didactic tasks of pedagogues cannot be carried out without ensuring the relationship between the teacher and the group of students.

Currently, interest in the problem of communication is increasing in our country and throughout the world. In the conditions of the market economy, communication between people is extremely important. Scientists associate communication with speech and communication, and also study it as a philosophical psychological problem. In particular, psychologist scientist V.N. Myasishev deeply researched the problem of communication and studied it as a whole process. That is, it analyzes how individuals influence each other through

communication as the most important way of perceiving each other. In his opinion: "A person can show his different sides and even opposite qualities in different relationships."

Russian researcher A.A. Bodalyev in his book "Person and Society" pays great attention to the issue of communication and notes that this problem is understudied. According to A.A. Bodalyev, "it is necessary to think in advance how to educate a person through communication." The role of personal qualities and moral qualities in successful communication is very important. In particular, if a person has well-developed positive qualities, moral standards and principles such as politeness, humility, humanity, truthfulness, conscientiousness occupy a sufficient place in his value system, communication with such a person the process is easy.

If these are the words about what you see or feel, then the need to talk about something arises.

It has been determined that the full satisfaction of a person's need for communication affects his work. People, their presence, the fact that there is an opportunity to talk to each other in this environment often increases a person's ability to work. , will find strength and additional will to work faster. True, if he likes the person next to him in this cooperation, if there is a feeling of mutual sympathy between them, then the person comes to work "as if he came to a holiday".

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